

Wealth Management Transformation in the Era of Digitalisation-Trends, Opportunities and Challenges in India

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Abstract

Wealth management is a holistic service that focuses on helping mid- to high-net-worth clients grow their wealth, manage their liability exposure and devise strategies to pass their wealth on to their designated heirs. It offers services like investment management and advice, comprehensive financial planning, tax planning and accounting services, estate planning, philanthropic planning, legal services & retirement planning. In the digital age, where incoming information is plentiful, and instantly available across a range of channels, it is imperative that both firms and their advisors adopt a proactive approach to client engagement and demonstrate that they are able to add real value to the investment equation. This research paper is based on the secondary data sourced from journals, magazines, articles and published reports regarding changes in wealth management due to digitalisation. The objective of the study is to find the opportunities and challenges faced by financial services firms in wealth management in India due to digital transformation. The study observed that Fintech firms are bringing new capabilities and approaches, and non-traditional tech competitors have established a higher bar for client expectations. This changing landscape, calls for wealth management firms to deliver more personalized and high-touch client experiences through digital engagement. Firms need to empower their advisors and clients with data, technology, and expertise that will boost advisor productivity, improve decision-making, deepen client engagement and optimize business performance. The three most significant challenges wealth management firms are facing i.e. commoditisation, fee compression and competition. These trends are forcing financial services firms to re-evaluate their digital offerings.

Keywords: Wealth Management, Digital Transformation, Financial Services Firm.

Introduction:

Wealth management (WM) or wealth management advisory (WMA) provides services to a wide array of clients ranging from affluent to high-net-worth (HNW) and ultra-high-net-worth (UHNW) individuals and families. It is a discipline which incorporates structuring and planning wealth to assist in growing, preserving, and protecting wealth, whilst passing it onto the family in a tax-efficient manner and in accordance with their wishes. Wealth management brings together tax planning, wealth protection, estate planning, succession planning, and family governance¹. Wealth management is a holistic service that focuses on helping mid- to high-net-worth clients grow their wealth, manage their liability exposure and devise strategies to pass their wealth on to their designated heirs. Wealth management services take a comprehensive approach to the financial situation of higher-net-worth clients, versus working with an advisor focused solely on

financial planning or investment management. Some typical services offered by wealth management firms include²:

- Investment management and advice
- Comprehensive financial planning
- Tax planning and accounting services
- Estate planning
- Philanthropic planning
- Legal services
- Retirement planning

Above all, wealth management offers best investment and advisory services under one roof to help you implement the most effective and tax-efficient financial plan at every stage of your life. The main advantage of wealth management is that it brings together many aspects of financial planning and money management in one comprehensive service centred on your unique needs and aspirations³.

The pace of digital transformation continues to accelerate. Driven by both structural trends and lockdowns, investors and advisors

now expect seamless Omni channel digital experiences. In the digital age, where incoming information is plentiful and instantly available across a range of channels, it is imperative that both firms and their advisors adopt a proactive approach to client engagement and demonstrate that they are able to add real value to the investment equation. And one way they are able to achieve these goals is by using digital wealth tools. Wealth management firms are entering a new phase of digital transformation. Fintech firms are bringing new capabilities and approaches, and non-traditional tech competitors have established a higher bar for client expectations. This changing landscape, calls for wealth management firms to deliver more personalized and high-touch client experiences through digital engagement. Firms need to empower their advisors and clients with data, technology, and expertise that will boost advisor productivity, improve decision-making, deepen client engagement and optimize business performance. These trends are forcing financial services firms to re-evaluate their digital offerings⁴.

Review of literature:

Margiono, A. (2021)⁵, This paper aims to identify the paths of digital transformation followed by companies facing disruption and offer recommendations for executives for choosing the appropriate path. This is a conceptual study. This paper identifies two paths of digital transformation. The offensive path is aggressive and involves the rapid acquisition of digital resources through portfolio investment and merger and acquisition tactics. The defensive path is relatively slow and relies on the organic growth of the digital capabilities of the incumbent companies over time. This paper identifies a number of potential factors affecting the choice of the transformation path taken by companies. Further studies can be conducted to investigate these contingent factors. This study describes the strategic paths available in a digital transformation and identifies the conditions that might justify a particular approach. This paper identifies two types of paths that are generally followed by companies aiming

digital transformation – offensive and defensive.

Plamen Dzhaparov (2022)⁶, The COVID-19 pandemic raises a number of questions for the Private Banking and Wealth Management Industry (PWM). The need for social distancing has created an entirely new situation facing this industry business model, traditionally based on continuous personal interaction between financial advisors and wealthy customers. Thus, private banks are facing the difficult task of raising digitalization to the top of their agenda as a matter of urgency. However, investing in digital tools and applications is only one side of the coin. Traditional institutions in the PWM sector have to deal with a number of other problems like “the skepticism of some clients, low satisfaction of others, difficulties with advisors, cyber threats, etc.

Raffaele Trequattrini & Alessandra Lardo (2022)⁷, This study aims to investigate the impact of digital technologies for intangible assets management. The authors analyse how technological innovations and regulations of intellectual property affect business models of companies or intellectual property rights (IPR) intensive industries to determine the impact of digital transformation on intangible assets management, highlighting emerging issues and future effects of the digital technology revolution. The authors use a case study method to answer our research questions. The authors use Soundreef Spa as our case study, a collecting company that develops technology for monitoring, collecting and maximising the earnings of songwriters and music publishers. The authors also elaborate and adopt the framework of the enhanced intellectual capital as the theoretical lens for presenting and analysing our case study, determining how the digital transformation caused business model innovation and more transparent and timely performance measurement in copyright-based companies. The analysis of Soundreef Spa’s business model allows us to demonstrate how using new technologies drives the performance measurement of copyright holders and improve the collecting societies’ performance, introducing a new key performance indicator.

This turning point is made possible by digital transformation and regulatory change. In the study, the authors demonstrate that digital transformation is able to enhance the intellectual capital of IPR-intensive companies introducing new ways to manage intangible assets and to measure performance.

Research Methodology: This research paper is based on the secondary data sourced from journals, magazines, articles and published reports of different agencies. Different aspects of use of clean and affordable energy for Sustainable development are studied in the light of reports by different agencies.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the changing concept of Wealth management.
2. To analyse the performance, status and challenges faced by fintech firms in India regarding wealth management.

Present Scenario in India:

The 21st century in India saw a spell of entrepreneurial ventures that has created an ever-growing High Net worth Individuals or HNWI's. India currently has the fourth-highest number of HNWIs in the Asia-Pacific region after Japan, China and Australia. The HNWI segment is the fastest growing segments leading to the growth of the wealth management industry, which could possibly be the most sought after career choice. The wealth management industry in India is growing rapidly mainly because of two reasons - the changing regulatory environment and increasing competition. Due to the growth rate, many big names have set up their wealth management division in India in the last few years. The existing business houses are also diversifying their services and venturing into wealth management. This trend is only going to spurt with India touted to become the third largest global economy by 2030. There are majorly three types of service providers for wealth management currently- Banks, Brokerage firms and Boutique advisory firms. Banks have larger investment distribution model which means they

concentrate on a larger investment portfolio. They cater to mid-level segment clients as well as the HNWI's. Brokerage firms focus on investing the customer's money majorly in shares and IPO, which are equity market products. Boutique advisory firms provide customized financial solutions to the clients who are majorly the ultra-HNWI and HNWI⁸.

Latest trends and Challenges & Future Prospects⁹:

The new generation of Millennial and Gen Z investors are digital-first and always connected. They want to be able to engage with financial advisors in real time across channels - be it video chat or text messages. They also expect 24/7 access to portfolio data and investment opportunities.

The future of wealth management will be hybrid i.e. a blend of physical and digital: Human connections and personal relationships have been the bedrock of the wealth management industry – and will continue to be so. Customers still want to be met with empathy, transparency, and warmth. But they're also looking for faster, more convenient, and seamless experiences. Digital solutions like robo-advisors and self-service investment portals will be key enablers.

Millennials are increasingly turning to non-traditional investment opportunities like passive investing, unlisted companies, private equity investing, antiques and collectibles, and most recently, non-fungible tokens (NFTs) and carbon credits. ESG investments are also on the rise. In the past few years, India has launched nine ESG-focused funds.

Regulators like the Securities and Exchange Board (SEBI) of India are paying closer attention to advisory firms' fee models, data security and privacy practices, AI/ML adoption, crypto-assets, and ESG (environmental, social, and governance) funds. Taxes are also expected to rise - a major concern for investors.

5. 'Financialisation of savings' is picking up speed: Historically, 95% of India's household wealth was stored in physical assets such as real estate and gold. But now, investors are moving away from physical savings to financial savings. They're more aware that an over-concentration of wealth in non-

financial assets can yield negative returns in the face of rising inflation.

Financial planning is becoming more holistic: The new generation of investors is combining financial goals with ethical and life goals. They're looking for more holistic investment options that include retirement planning, impact investing, estate planning, and social welfare.

Hyper-personalisation is the need of the hour: No longer does a one-size-fits-all approach work with investors. They expect curated, contextual and bespoke offerings that are closely aligned with their needs. Whether its investment products, marketing emails, or call centre service, every customer touch point needs to be personalised to gain customer loyalty and trust.

Challenges:

Clients are changing: Wealth Managers face a challenge on two fronts. Firstly, retaining assets across generations, and secondly, upgrading propositions for digitally savvy investors with different service expectations

Advice and discretionary margins are pressured: Comfort in self-servicing, desire for new products (typically requiring less advice or discretion) and more retail friendly vehicles, is on the rise. The market for full discretion or advice appears at risk

Regulation creating opportunities and threats: Access to client financial data can make the advice process more efficient and reduce barriers to entry; in parallel, firms are under pressure to reduce fees and increase transparency

Competition is intensifying: The number of traditional firms working on new propositions is growing and "Digital Wealth Managers" (e.g. Scalable, Nutmeg) are reaching some scale¹⁰.

In addition to it, other significant challenges wealth management firms are facing i.e. commoditisation, fee compression and competition.

Opportunities:

Although digital is seen as a key priority for the vast majority of Wealth Managers, there are many internal factors such as legacy technology, an inconsistent digital strategy and resistance to change that is holding back transformational change. Initially, wealth management services were provided by Chartered Accountants who also served as investment advisors for families and

individuals. Since then, India, as a developing young economy, has seen an increase in the number of affluent people looking for investment opportunities as per capita income has risen. This, in turn, resulted in a technologically-driven evolution of wealth management in India. Today, the affluent middle class is rapidly expanding. With nearly 80% of households predicted to be middle-income by 2030, the country's high net worth individual (HNI) population is expected to increase by 75% to 6.11 Lakhs in 2025. Ultra-high net worth individuals (UHNIs) are expected to increase by 63% during the same period. This burgeoning increase in disposable income indicates the wealth management sector's potential for growth. To meet the increased demand for investment advice, technology has become an essential component of the industry. Investment advice tailored to the needs of individual clients is no longer just an analogue process where dedicated wealth managers manually map portfolios of individuals and give personalised advice¹¹.

Suggestions:

For winning the loyalty of this cohort requires re-imagining traditional investment ecosystems as those which are more tailored to their needs. Advisors should also embrace digital tools and process automation to be more productive and respond faster to customer needs. Fintech firms should be proactively prepared with a strong compliance program and system of controls.

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